

Title: the outsourcing as a strategy to help the new entrepreneurs.

Evidence from CNAC dispositive in Tlemcen region in the period 2005-2012

Axis 5: Outsourcing and Entrepreneurship

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Abstract:

The entrepreneurship is the most important engine of economic growth in the world. Following different problems faced by the entrepreneurs, the outsourcing is a process to lead the entrepreneurs to look for solutions for the problems. We will try in this paper to give a quick view of the contribution of the CNAC dispositive as a financial dispositive to launch SME/SMI in the Tlemcen region in the period 2005-2012 in the first side and to focus in the important role of the outsourcing as a strategy to help the new entrepreneurs to face the barriers in the future. There for, this paper will include in the first part the entrepreneurship as an engine for the economic growth. In the second part, a global view of the CNAC dispositive and exploratory study in the region of Tlemcen in the period of 2005-2012. In the third part, we will see the outsourcing as a way to avoid the future problem in addition to achieve the economies of scale.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, CNAC, Tlemcen, outsourcing

الملخص:

تعتبر المقاولاتية من اهم المحركات لدفع عجلة التنمية الاقتصادية في العالم، نظرا للمشاكل التي يواجهها المقاول، يعتبر التعاقد الخارجي من العمليات للأخذ بيد المقاول للبحث على الحلول، سوف نحاول في هذه الورقة البحثية التطرق الى دور الصندوق الوطني للتأمين على البطالة كمؤسسة الدعم المالي للدعم المؤسسات الصغيرة و المتوسطة في ولاية تلمسان في المدة 2005-2012 في الاول ثم الاشارة الى دور التعاقد الخارجي كاستراتيجية لإعانة المقاولين لتخطي العقبات في المستقبل، و لهذا، تحتوي هذه الورقة في الاول المقاولاتية من اطارها النظري، ثم دور الصندوق الوطني للتأمين على البطالة في خلق المقاولين في تلمسان في المدة 2005-2012، في العنصر الثالث، نتطرق الى دور التعاقد الخارجي لمواجهة الازمات في المستقبل و للوصول الى الاقتصاديات السلمية.

الكلمات المفتاحية : المقولانية، الصندوق الوطني للتأمين على البطالة، تلمسان ، التعاقد الخارجي.

"PROGRESSIVE ENTREPRENEURS REALIZE THE UNSTOPPABLE POWER OF
OUTSOURCING TO HANDLE ASPECTS OF THEIR BUSINESS THAT ARE ESSENTIAL
BUT SIMPLY DON'T MAKE SENSE FOR THEM TO DEAL WITH PERSONALLY,"

DAVID WALSH

Introduction:

In the economy, we find that entrepreneurship from the important engines to launch the economic growth in developed and developing countries through their different advantages. However, in different moment, we find that different entrepreneurs or different firms faces problems and barriers push them in the first side to give more fees for unknown results, and to louse their market part from the second side and to deteriorate the image of the enterprise. In this point and to avoid this negative results and following the experiences of different successful entrepreneurs, outsourcing can deliver major benefits from reducing costs and improving quality control environment ...etc. From the importance of outsourcing, engaging with an effective outsourcing partner has proven to be critical component in the successful up scaling and expansion of many world-renowned. There for we will tried in this paper to give in the first part a global study about entrepreneurship. In the second part, we will discuss about CNAC as a financial dispositive to create entrepreneurs. In the third part, we will try to clarify the definition of the outsourcing, the different types and advantages of the outsourcing. In the conclusion, we will give some ideas about the importance of the outsourcing for the Algerian entrepreneur.

I. Entrepreneurship: Literature review

1.1. Definition:

According to (Lewis 1955) 'economic growth is bound to slow unless there is an adequate supply of entrepreneurs looking out for new ideas, and willing to take the risk of introducing them'.

To pursue the economic growth in the world, entrepreneurship is one of the important key factors for the growth of the different economies. According to (Stefanescu and On 2012), they find that sustainable entrepreneurship is related with the sustainable development. In addition to push the entrepreneurship following different studies to know the different

obstacles and the different barriers faced by the individuals to create their own small enterprises. According to (Bourouaha Abdelhamid, Maliki Samir Baha Ed-dine, and Derbal Abdelkader 2014), they mention that the individual find different obstacles related especially with the sources of finance.

The entrepreneurship can get different meaning and definitions as products of environment like provision of venture capital and an interesting growth in demand in the market, or personal attributes like risk taking propensity and need for achievement (Stam 2009).

From the view of Schumpeter, “the entrepreneurship entail and continue the change from the introduction of shifting or transforming new paradigm to create an innovative product or achieve INNOVATION rather than particular occupation”(Joseph Alois Schumpeter 1939).

1.2.Types of entrepreneurship:

There are two important types of entrepreneurship, and these two types are related with the way of becoming entrepreneur:

A. Necessity entrepreneurship:

Under this type of entrepreneurship, we will discover the individuals who did not find available free jobs (paid employee) there for they were obliged to become entrepreneurs rather than staying unemployed.

B. Opportunity entrepreneurship:

In the business studies, the entrepreneur is the person who perceive an opportunity, and creates an organization to pursue it (Bygrave and Hofer 1991, 14). Therefore, the opportunity entrepreneurship contains all entrepreneur who became entrepreneur through an opportunity that they perceive. Therefore, the individual will invest to exploit the opportunity that it perceives rather than becoming paid-employee even if has the available paid-job because he finds that paid-job do not allow him to exploit all his skills. This entrepreneurial opportunity is ideas, actions, and all beliefs that enable the individuals to produce product or give services in the absence of the current markets of them(Stam 2009). The opportunity entrepreneur may include individuals who aims to maintain or improve their income, or to enhance their independence(Siri Roland Xavier et al. 2013).

1.3.The importance of entrepreneurship:

The entrepreneurship plays an important role in the economy of the state; we can touch its importance from different ways such as:

- Generating employment and economic growth:

Following the study of (A. Roy Thurik et al. 2008; BOUROUAHA Abdelhammid 2014), the entrepreneurship is the source of creating employment and the economic growth.

- New innovations with new products or new services(Stephan F. Gohmann and Jose M. Fernandez 2013).
- Entrepreneurship as a process of the Knowledge spillovers.
- Increasing the productivity by increase competition.
- Mitigating the unemployment.
- Creating new product or new production process.

1.4.The entrepreneurship facilities in Algeria:

According to the importance of the entrepreneurship and their role in pushing up the level of the economy in addition to reducing the levels of the unemployment and poverty, the Algerian government gives an interest to this factor that is entrepreneurship by:

- Looking for the incentives that it enhances the individual to become entrepreneur:

From these different incentives, we find that: becoming self-employee, own boss, feel that it contributes in the economy, the best role in the society, insuring a good future for the children, creating wealth, exploiting personal skills are the most likely incentives that the individual want to get them.

- Looking for the different obstacles and barriers that it faced the previous enterprises

Through these obstacles, the Algerian government could create mechanism by taking in consideration these obstacles to make the way so easy for the individual to become entrepreneur.

From the different facilities that the Algerian government created them to enhance entrepreneurship and curb unemployment, it creates different mechanisms to promote individuals with skills or diploma to become entrepreneurs. There are two kinds of mechanisms:

According to the highest rate of unemployment, the Focus all their interest to create a mechanism that it allows the unemployed people with such skills to create their own enterprises

II. Outsourcing as strategy for new entrepreneurs, definitions and types:

2.1. Definition

The concept "outsourcing" came from American Glossary 'outside resourcing' and it dates back to at least 1981. Outsourcing sometimes involves transferring employees and assets from one firm to another, but not always. Outsourcing is also the practice of handing over control of public services to for-profit corporations (Jamieson, Dave 2013).

Outsourcing includes both foreign and domestic contracting (Hira and Hira 2005, 67–96) and sometimes includes offshoring (relocating a business function to another country). According to (Paul Davies 2004), the Financial savings from lower international labor rates can provide a major motivation for outsourcing or offshoring. Outsourcing from the important strategies to handle firms to do not fall in problems and mistakes could finish their sustainability.

2.2. Types of outsourcing processes:

In the first, outsourcing can be seen as time-consuming in the first because it does not bring anything for the firms. From another side, outsource process as relationship that provide access to industry knowledge, best practice and the new ideas.

There for, it is necessary for the new entrepreneurs to follow the outsourcing partners to reach to the economies of scale. The chart below presents the three important types of the outsourcing:

A. Business process outsourcing (BPO)

According to (Tas and Sunder 2004), the business process outsourcing is a subset of outsourcing that involves the contracting of the operations and responsibilities of a specific business process to a third-party service provider? Originally, this was associated with manufacturing firms.

BPO is typically categorized into back office outsourcing, which includes *internal business functions* such as human resources or finance and accounting, and front office outsourcing, which includes *customer-related services* such as contact center services.

BPO that is contracted outside a company's country is called offshore outsourcing. BPO that is contracted to a company's neighboring (or nearby) country is called nearshore outsourcing.

Often the business processes are information technology-based, and are referred to as **ITES-BPO**, where ITES stands for Information Technology Enabled Service (Nellis and Parker 2006). To summarize the business process outsourcing, the circle below presents the different operations of BPO for the enterprise in general:

Figure 1: BPO Operations

B. Legal process outsourcing (LPO)

The legal process outsourcing refers to the practice of a law firm or corporation obtaining legal support services from an outside law firm or legal support services company (LPO provider). When the LPO provider is based in another country, the practice is called offshoring and involves the practice of outsourcing any activity except those where personal presence or contact is required, e.g. appearances in court and face-to-face negotiations. When the LPO provider is based in the same country, the practice of outsourcing includes agency work and other services requiring a physical presence, such as court appearances (Tim Lemieux 2015).

C. Knowledge process outsourcing (KPO)

Sanchez describes in his paper (Carlos Sanchez 2010) that the outsourcing of core information-related business activities which are competitively important or form an integral part of a company's value chain. According to (Matt Wade 2015) KPO requires advanced analytical and technical skills as well as a high degree of specialist expertise.

According to (Ghosh, 2009) KPO is a continuation of Business process outsourcing, yet with rather more of business complexity. To be successful in Knowledge process outsourcing, a lot of guide is required from interorganizational system. The figure below summarizes the knowledge process outsourcing:

Figure 2: knowledge process outsourcing operations

In addition to this definition, there are other processes outsourcing such as: *Recruitment process outsourcing RPO*, *Engineering process outsourcing EPO*.

2.3.The outsourcing for all levels of the firms:

From the side of the entrepreneurs, they see that outsourcing strategies is reserved just for the big business. However, and following the technological growth, it made it more accessible tool for all levels of firms and businesses because it has a great impact on the growth, productivity and bottom lines of the firms in the future. From another way, the technology opens the doors for the accessibility of extremely qualified professionals who have decided or

been forced to leave the corporate world. Therefore, there will be as outsourcing partners for the small firm they could work from any place in the world.

2.4. Advantages and disadvantages of outsourcing:

the three important questions that each firm wants to outsource or look for partner to outsource are:

-What and how many services to outsource?

- What to look for in a provider?

-What benefits outsourcing brings?

✓ There for, according to (Gilley and Rasheed 2000), from the important advantages of outsourcing:

- Outsourcing firms often achieve cost advantages relative to vertically integrated firms. Through outsourcing, manufacturing costs decline and investment in plant and equipment can be reduced. This reduced investment in manufacturing capacity lowers fixed costs and leads to a lower break-even point. Thus, outsourcing may be an attractive method of improving a firm's financial performance, especially in the short run.

- Firms focusing on outsourcing can switch suppliers as new, more cost effective technologies become available.

- Outsourcing noncore activities allow the firm to increase managerial attention and resource allocation to those tasks that it does best and to rely on management teams in other organizations to oversee tasks at which the outsourcing firm is at a relative disadvantage.

- Outsourcing tends to promote competition among outside suppliers, thereby ensuring availability of higher-quality goods and services in the future.

To summarize the different advantages of the outsourcing, the picture below demonstrates the different advantages of outsourcing for the enterprise:

Figure 3:outsourcing advantages

✓ With these advantages, there are in the second side some disadvantages that are cited as bellow:

- One of the most serious threats resulting from a reliance on outsourcing is declining innovation by the outsourcer. Outsourcing can lead to a loss of long-run research and development (R&D) competitiveness, because it is often used as a substitute for innovation.
- The cost savings associated with outsourcing may not be as great as they seem, especially with respect to foreign suppliers. The transaction costs associated with repeated market-based transactions.
 - Outsourcing requires a shift in overhead allocation to those products or activities that remain in-house. This reallocation of overhead degrades the apparent financial performance of the remaining products or activities and raises their vulnerability to subsequent outsourcing, perhaps leading to an outsourcing spiral.
 - Tariffs are another danger associated with outsourcing, as are increases in the difficulty of bringing back into the firm activities that may now add value because of market shifts.

III. The CNAC mechanism:

As we mention above, and according to the importance of entrepreneurship in the economic growth. In addition to the different studies that are turn around the difficulties that it faces the individual to create own enterprise, the Algerian government start to invest in this sector by taking the mission of financing the new enterprises created by the individual through creating different mechanisms. From these mechanisms, we find that the CNAC from the importing dispositive. The idea of creating CNAC dispositive is to help the involuntary unemployed people in the period after the shock in the hydrocarbon prices; it was created through the presidential decree 188-94 in July 06, 1994. In December 30, 2003, it started to finance the new project created by the unemployed.

3.1. The CNAC facilities:

To facilitate the way for the unemployed to become entrepreneur, the Algerian government follows different facilities to enhance the unemployed for entrepreneurship. From these facilities, we find different kinds that are related with the different steps of the creation of the enterprise.

A. Before the creation:

The CNAC mechanism takes different to facilitate the procedure for the individuals before the creation of the enterprises by a formation.

- *The formation:*

According to the importance that it face the entrepreneurship education over the world, in addition to (von Graevenitz, Harhoff, and Weber 2010) where he found that student who has entrepreneurship education are more likely to be entrepreneurs rather than the ones how has not this courses. Also, according to (Sondari 2014) who find that the entrepreneurship education gets an important role in creating entrepreneurial intention in the student.

B. In the creation process:

After the step of the formation where the individuals have got the important information about the world that they will inter, the step of the folder creation. In this step, the Algerian government makes other facilities in the way of reducing the barriers in the face of the unemployed of becoming entrepreneur. This reduction characterized in:

C. The CSVF¹ committee:

Before, in the first step of the procedure of the creation, the individuals find different obstacles in the way of satisfying the bankers for the credibility of the project, where in some situation, the entrepreneur was obliged to use his personal relation to get the loan of the bank. There for, the government creates the CSVF committee that it contains delegates from the banks, the CNAC mechanism, and the civic state delegates in addition to the entrepreneur. For that, this committee from the important facilities lead the individuals to get loan to launch his project.

- **Reduction in the personal part:**

From the big obstacles that it faced the unemployed to get loan and become entrepreneur through CNAC mechanisms is the personal part. Because, in the first the procedure of financing the project was as in the table below:

Table 1: Segmentation of sum of loan in the first

	Personal part	CNAC part	Banc Part
Less than 5.000.000,00 AD	5%	25%	70%
Between 5.000.000,00 AD and 10.000.000,00 AD	10%	20%	70%

Source: www.cnac.dz

After that, and according to the different demands of the individuals how have entrepreneurial skills but they do not have much money for the personal part. It reduced the personal part to a minimum sum as it is presented in the table to allow the maximum number of unemployed to get loan and create their own enterprises:

Table 2: new segmentation of the sum of loan

	Personal part	CNAC part	Banc Part
Less than 5.000.000,00 AD	1%	29%	70%
Between 5.000.000,00 AD and 10.000.000,00 AD	2%	28%	70%

Source : <http://www.mf.gov.dz/article/300/Grands-Dossiers/255/DISPOSITIF-CNAC.html>

¹ CSVF : comité de Suivre, Validation et de Financement.

- **Reduction in the interest rate:**

To satisfy the needs of the individuals wanting to become entrepreneur, the Algerian government offers some special reduction in the interest rate in addition to the reduction that it touches all individuals who get loan from CNAC dispositive. This reduction related with two points:

- ✓ **Sector of activity:**

The CNAC mechanism offers reduction in the rate of interest in normal sector with 50%. The rate of reduction could be equal to 75% if the sector of activity one of these sectors:

Agriculture, fishing and irrigation sector.

This policy used to enhance the individuals how has such skills and experience in these domains to invest in these sectors.

- ✓ **Place of activity:**

Through the diversified regions in the Algerian countries where the big surface is so difficult to stay in, the Algerian government gives these places some special important in the goal of investing in these regions. There for, the rate of decreases is as follows:

In the special areas, the rate of decrease in the interest rate is 90%

In the South and high plateau, the rate of the decrease is 75%.

D. After the creation of the enterprise:

To complete the procedure of felicitating the way for the new entrepreneurs in the market, the Algerian government thinks also in the market that they will inter, therefor it creates a special part for this category of the entrepreneurs:

- **Create a part of them in the market:**

According to the different obstacles, that it faced the enterprises especially in the sector of manufacturing and construction. Following the presidential decree 12-23 in January 18, 2012, The Algerian government makes rate of 20% of the offered project for the new entrepreneurs as a step to help them in the market in front of the high level of competition.

- **Taxes reduction:**

After the creation of the enterprise and through the previous obstacles faced by the new enterprises that are related with the taxes, the Algerian government exempts the new entrepreneurs in the first three years from the taxes below:

IRG²: Exemption from the tax on gross income

IBS³: Exemption from tax on the profits of the company

TAP⁴: Exemption from the tax on professional activity

TFPB⁵: Exemption from real estate tax based on property

3.2.Exploratory view of CNAC entrepreneurs in Tlemcen 2005-2012:

The CNAC mechanism contributes with an important rate in creating entrepreneurship in Tlemcen. The figure bellow shows the growth of the number of entrepreneurs.

Figure 4: growth of entrepreneurs through CNAC in Tlemcen 2005-2012

Source: www.cnac.dz

In the first, we found that the number of entrepreneurs was 41 entrepreneurs. From this point, we understand that the individuals are interested to be self-employee. According to the important rate of the female in our society, we found also that she enters to the entrepreneurial world inside the man. The table below presents the segmentation of the number of the entrepreneurs per gender:

² IRG : Impôts sur revenu global

³ IBS : Impôts sur les bénéfices des sociétés

⁴ TAP : Taxe sur l'activité professionnelle

⁵ TFPB : taxe foncière sur les propriétés bâties

Table 3: segmentation of CNAC entrepreneurs by gender

Gender	Number	Rate %
Male	2137	89.12 %
Female	261	10.88 %
Total	2398	100 %

Source: www.cnac.dz

From this table, we understand that the female gets the ability as the man to get loan and to create her enterprises, to show to the world that she also apt to take risks as the man. Also, she has got also her personal skills in some special sector, for that she finds the financial mechanisms to finance her projects.

3.3.Growth of entrepreneurs per sector of activity:

From the different facilities, that the Algerian government makes to encourage the individual to become entrepreneur is to allow him to choose the sector of activity according to his desirous. As we show in the table below, the entrepreneurship through CNAC mechanism, touch different sectors. From the ones that it does not need just driving license, in the case for the enterprises of transport to the sectors of industry and construction where it is necessary the existence of the experiences, skills and special diploma to launch an enterprise in these kinds of activities.

Table 4: growth of entrepreneurs per sector of activity in Tlemcen 2005-2012

year	industry	agriculture	Services	transport	handicrafts	construction	total
2005	2	5	7	16	4	7	41
2006	5	13	7	47	5	9	86
2007	5	8	4	74	6	14	111
2008	2	13	7	98	5	9	134
2009	2	6	6	162	4	16	196
2010	0	7	5	228	2	11	253
2011	1	5	8	488	7	14	523
2012	13	49	25	925	5	37	1054
total	30	106	69	2038	38	117	2398

Source: www.cnac.dz

From the table above, we find that the number of the new entrepreneurs in the last year (2012) is the most important with more than 1000 new entrepreneurs. As a result, we understand that the different of the CSVF committee and the reduction in the personal part push the individuals to create their own enterprises.

For the different sectors of activity, we find that the majority of the enterprises are focuses in the transport sector with more than 85%.

For more detail, the figure below clarifies the segmentation of the entrepreneurs by sector of activity:

Figure 5: segmentation of enterprises per sector of activity

Source: www.cnac.dz

As we said before, the bog rate of the entrepreneurs focused in the transport sector according to the facility in the folder of getting loan. In the second rate, we find that the enterprises in construction and manufacturing in the second place with 117 entrepreneurs, this is related to the facility of 20% of project for the new entrepreneurs.

The agriculture placed in the third place with 106 according to the difficulties of the sector of activity.

Table 5: segmentation of sector of activity per gender

	Industries	Agriculture	Services	Transport	Handicraft	Manufacturing
Male	22	81	37	1859	24	114
Female	8	25	32	179	14	3

Source: www.cnac.dz

The table above shows the segmentation of entrepreneurs through sector of activity and gender. We find that the female entrepreneurs founded in all sector as the male entrepreneurs, the matter that it confirms the ability of taking risks in front of the man, but with different rates according to the skills of the gender. For example, the rate of the female entrepreneurs is nearly like the male entrepreneur's rate (32 entrepreneurs and 37 entrepreneurs respectively). In addition, the female entrepreneurs contribute also in the domain of handicraft by exploiting their personal skills as hairdresser and dressmaker.

Conclusion:

We cannot say that outsourcing is the same for all firms. Following the experience of some entrepreneurs, outsourcing time is when the entrepreneurs want to grow. There for and following this paper where we tried to give in the first a global overview of the entrepreneurship, in the second part the entrepreneurship in Algeria and the dispositive CNAC from the financial dispositive created from the state to launch the entrepreneurship and to foster the economic growth. But, following some interviews, we touch that the new entrepreneurs find strong obstacles in the professional life. These obstacles are following the absence of the outsourcing processes in our societies. There for, we demonstrate the outsourcing as processes to help the new entrepreneurs in their professional lives from the first side, and to remind the Algerian state that there are new processes to launch the entrepreneurs from bad situation to economic of scale due to the important role of outsourcing processes.

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